

#5

Evaluation & Impact Assessment

**NEEDS REGISTER: RECORDING
STAKEHOLDERS NEEDS & ASSESSING
RESPONSIVENESS**

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>ENGAGING & INCENTIVISING CREATING EVALUATION & IMPACT ASSESSMENT</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>Used at the beginning of interactive innovation, and iteratively throughout project/initiative to revisit/change/rotate roles of actors in projects/networks/initiatives as necessary.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Any size</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>No technical skills required.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>Depends on size of stakeholder network</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>It may be preferable to maintain the register online, so internet and MS Office software.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tools # 1, 2, 3, 6.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Image source: [Roman Synkevych on Unsplash](#)

Purpose

This tool is used to:

- Identify and record stakeholder needs in a register, accessible to participants of interactive innovation.
- Mobilise a multi-actor team to be continuously attuned to stakeholder needs, by: requesting them to seek out and record stakeholder needs; and by providing them with a register they can consult when trying to understand stakeholder needs
- Provide an evidence-based reference source to assess how well project/initiative activities are responding to stakeholder needs and to make necessary adjustments.

Background and Logic

Interactive innovation projects and initiatives are often publicly funded, in order to produce benefits for society. Multi-actor teams are tasked with representing different cohorts of society, bringing different types of knowledge to the interactive innovation process & responding to the needs of different cohorts. To respond to the needs of different stakeholders effectively, strategically and in an evidence-based way, it is necessary to identify and record the needs of different stakeholders, and to periodically assess how project activities respond to their needs. When stakeholder needs are properly understood and responded to, stakeholders' needs can drive and focus the innovation process, and, ultimately, stakeholders are more likely to engage with and adopt the new products and processes that emerge from the innovation process.

This tool provides a simple approach for identifying & recording stakeholder needs and for appraising how well project activities are responding to stakeholder needs. The needs' register can be updated to include new stakeholder types and their needs. Project activities can be periodically assessed through the lens of: whose stakeholders' needs are and are not being met; are there particular types of needs not being met etc.

This tool can be used in conjunction with Tool #1, which maps stakeholder types; Tool #2, which assigns tasks & roles to project actors (tasks such as engaging with stakeholders); and Tool #3, which creates persona models of stakeholder types. This tool complements these tools by providing a comprehensive register of the needs of wide-ranging stakeholders.

Materials

- Short questionnaire to assess needs
- MS word document or Excel file.

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

Step 1: Preparation

- Explain the purpose, logic and background of the tool.
- Optionally, show the 'multi-actor work' animation, which shows the importance of responding to stakeholders' needs, and their different operational contexts. The animation could also be sent by email/ WhatsApp in advance of the meeting, helping them to prepare for the content of the meeting.
- Initially, some information on needs can be collected from within the multi-actor group, which is representative of some stakeholder communities. Asking participants of a multi-actor group to think about stakeholder needs provokes them to think and work in a stakeholder-oriented way.
- Ask participants, considering the particular topic/s of the project, what are key stakeholder needs from their perspectives? Ask participants to note these on post-its and affix them to a flipchart/whiteboard.
- Show an example of a needs register, as pictured.

Step 2: Identify Opportunities to Engage with Stakeholders

- For projects that have begun (and have a planned work programme):
- Look through the programme to identify all opportunities / events where interaction with stakeholders will occur.
- Identify them on a timeline, with dates (months or quarters suffice where exact dates haven't yet been decided)
- For projects that have not yet begun, identify imminent opportunities to engage with stakeholders and make a plan, using a time-line with dates, of realistic opportunities to take.

5	Ireland	Teagasc	Meat products from animals that are almost entirely grass fed are not perceived by many producers and industry professionals as products that can potentially command a higher price if production practices and producer attributes
6	Ireland	Teagasc	Innovative solutions to market/process/connect partners in the raw milk value chain
7	Belgium	ISP	Selling through the internet of fresh products is the less developed within online sales. However a lot of trials are made, people are talking about it, ... but many fail. Not a lot is known about costs, failures, learning and examples
8	Belgium	UGENT	In order to assemble producers and consumers in short food chain community initiatives, many producers encounter the power of the Auction. As such, for producers it is most important to liberate them from the Auction' yoke
9	Italy	UNIFG	Preserving local farming and processing traditions as guarantee of higher products quality. Locals are very concerned about the adopted methods for processing farm products and they mostly prefer to buy handmade food' or simple
10	Italy	UNIFG	The price of traditional and local products is too high if they are sold through long chain and long chain is not a guarantee of traditional and local product for the consumers. To this extent producers aim to reduce the distance with th
11	Italy	UNIFG	Innovative social approach for boosting and encouraging young farmers and any unemployed people in getting together in order to develop an innovative business idea on short food supply chain enterprise. Southern areas mostly
12	Hungary	CERHAS	CERHAS/1. For scattered small producers (even within the same sector) it is difficult to sell their products on the market because of the size and the unevenness of their production throughout the year. Innovative good practices (p
13	Hungary	CERHAS	CERHAS/2. Small producers (and people in general) living and working in isolation in desolating regions often don't appreciate their own environment, traditions, human and natural resources, etc. Some kind of producers' network
14	Hungary	CERHAS	CERHAS/3. By taking the aspects of social responsibility into account, through using the given sources of a region (human, environmental, technical, etc.) in a way that it also gives a hand for the disadvantaged ones, quality prod.
15	Hungary	CERHAS	CERHAS/4. The existing demand for fresh products in the market of cities has been present for a long time, as the people living there, has no chance for reaching high quality, backyard products, or the supply is not continuous. A
16	Hungary	CBHU	The promotion of the traditional products is needed for their success. Some of the case the individual products do not bring success, so collaboration among the different actors along the supply chain can be a good solution for mut.
17	Hungary	CBHU	Valorisation, social sustainability: Efficiencies and process innovations, achievement of efficiencies through collaboration, Valorisation: multi-actor co-design approach, tradition used to added value, Contractual agreements betwee
18	UK	EFB	By looking at the certificates that confirm the organic and quality aspect of the products. Novel approach of marketing - connections with local primary producers.
19	UK	EFB	
20	UK	MCA	There is a shortage of local abattoir facilities and even where they are present they are comparatively expensive, heavily oversubscribed / lack capacity and are difficult for local meat producers to get stock killed when it is finished
21	UK	MCA	In the UK it is very difficult / almost impossible for new entrants into agriculture to gain access to land and buildings to develop SFC businesses. Competition for land for sale or rent is a significant issue and anything which become
22	Italy	CONFAGRICOLTURA	Simplifying all the procedures to be a young farmer start up , beginning from the ownership...
23	Italy	CONFAGRICOLTURA	Establishing a systematic calendar of local fairs and events to build a Marketing strategy of the local production/ by territory
24	Italy	CONFAGRICOLTURA	Reinforcing the relationships with the local universities for alternate scholarship/farming and social agricultu
25	Italy	CONFAGRICOLTURA	Readding value to the local landscapes through comparing photos, pictures, paintings
26	Italy	CONFAGRICOLTURA	Recovering ancient and rare vegetables and animals, restarting their production and rediscovering some population collective participation and consensus and sympathy
27	Italy	CONFAGRICOLTURA	
28	Denmark	SEGES	How do farmers efforts regarding sustainability creat value in short supply chain
29		SEGES	
30	Slovakia	CLS	The main need of all small and medium Slovak farmers is to actually get entrance in the sector including the lack of the free land (most of the land is rented by the big farms and for long period of time)
31	Czech Republ	WIRELESSINFO	The Czech Republic has the fourth most densely network of hypermarkets in Europe. Large stores over 400 square meters represent 80 percent of total turnover, which is the most in Central Europe. The high concentration of chai
32	Slovakia	CLS	Information support of the local products is highly needed to explain why these products have a higher value as other (economical, environmental, health and social factors). The high concentration of chai
33	Slovakia	CLS	Organisation of local clusters of small supply chains actors to reduce the costs of all stakeholders and make the local food producer stronger and competitive
34	Slovakia	CLS	The pressing of the big player in the price formation on milk is very high, farmers need possibility to sell dairy products for the fair price
35	Slovakia	CLS	The possibilities got the state support for the farmers from western countries is much higher as for farmers in Slovakia, this reduce the interest to the agricultural business and the quantity of local food on the market

Step 3: Identify Ways of Collecting Information on Needs

- Ways of collecting needs – from stakeholders themselves – are diverse and suitable ways can be identified for any given project/initiative:
 - » For each of the opportunities/events identified, facilitate a discussion around:
 - » What are the ways in which we can easily elicit information on different stakeholders' needs at the event? E.g. a very short entry or exit survey, or deploying project actors to engage in conversation with stakeholders to find out what their key needs are (in the context of the prospective/project's focus). Note the ways suggested by participants on post-its beside the relevant opportunity on the time-line.
 - » Emphasise to participants the need to make the experience as burdenless as possible for stakeholders (i.e. completing a lengthy survey on needs at each project event is not likely to be favourable for stakeholders)
 - » Considering the ways participants have suggested (for each opportunity on the time-line), what are the most effective/realistic/feasible to implement/popular to participants?
 - » Taking all opportunities may not be necessary. For example, some opportunities/events may take place very close to each other and involve the same participants. Which events are the most opportunistic and what selection of events are necessary to gain thorough, broad and updated information on stakeholder needs?
 - » Circle those that are favoured and selected by participants.

Step 4: Creation of a Plan to Collect Stakeholders' Needs

- For each of the selected events/ways to collect information on stakeholder needs, create a plan of who will undertake what during the opportunities/ at the events, taking into account their workloads around the particular dates.
- If necessary, revisit the time-line and select alternative events/ways that are more feasible to implement.
- Consider allocating participants to specific stakeholder cohorts to leverage opportunities and avoid:

- » Participants may have existing relationships with/understandings of cohorts that can be leveraged when it comes to understanding stakeholder needs.
- » Participants, when repeatedly engaging with particular cohorts, can actively avoid engaging with individual stakeholders repeatedly to avoid 'respondent fatigue'. Or, participants can strategically engage with actors to understand how their needs may be changing (perhaps in reflection of their engagement with the project).

Step 5: Plan Implementation & Creation of the Register

- The register can be initially populated by the needs identified by project actors in Step 1.
- The structure of the register is as pictured, but can be modified according to needs of the project. It can be stored on a shared drive for easy access & updating.
- As each event in the plan for collecting needs is implemented, the implementers add the collected information to the register.
- The register should be mentioned at project meetings, and participants may add further stakeholder type.
- The implementation plan can be modified and extended as necessary (if further stakeholder types and events are added).

Step 6: Assessment of Project Activities According to Stakeholder Needs

- The register should be regularly visited and perused in the context of project activities:
 - » How do our activities respond to stakeholder needs?
 - » Which stakeholders?
 - » Which needs do they respond to?
 - » Are some stakeholders and some needs responded to than others?
- Project activities may require modification on the basis of the assessment.
- The implementation plan and register shows how project actors have gathered evidence of stakeholder needs, and of the needs themselves.
- A record of how project activities have been assessed through the lens of stakeholder needs should be kept.

